

Internship proposal: Pulse waveform shape metrics from harmonic analysis in retinal Doppler holography

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January 21, 2026

Abstract

Retinal Doppler holography enables seconds-long, dye-free measurements of beat-resolved blood-flow velocity waveforms in principal retinal arteries and veins. To translate these information-rich signals into trial-ready endpoints, waveform shape must be reduced to *auditable, transportable* numbers that remain stable across operators, sites, devices, and software versions. This internship will specify and implement a concise **Tier-1** panel of pulse-shape descriptors computed from the *complex cardiac harmonics* of a beat-locked velocity waveform. The panel combines (i) **dimensionless harmonic metrics** (e.g., second-harmonic prominence, richness beyond the fundamental, and spectral decay slope), (ii) **shift-invariant phase organisation** descriptors (phase-coupling / “shape phase” and phase-based delays), and (iii) **band-limited, harmonic-derived time summaries** (e.g., centroid and VTI-style stroke-distance partitions) derived deterministically from the accepted harmonics. All metrics will be reported only under explicit **visit- and harmonic-level quality gates** (harmonic SNR/coverage, beat stability, phase dispersion), with coverage indicators and bootstrap uncertainty, and packaged as benchmark-grade, versioned outputs integrated into the open-source analysis pipeline and the standard microvascular health report.

1 Context and motivation

Retinal Doppler holography yields information-rich arterial and venous pulse-shaped velocity waveforms in principal retinal vessels within a few seconds [1] (Fig. 1). The translational step is to convert these waveforms into *endpoints*: stable quantities whose meaning is explicit, auditable, and comparable across operators, sites, devices, and software versions. We adopt a Tier-1, *infrastructure-first* philosophy: the metric definitions, validity domains, and reporting conventions are engineered upstream, and the pipeline deterministically enforces them downstream.

Figure 1: Example workflow and outputs: Doppler holography map with segmented principal retinal vessels; beat-resolved arterial/venous velocity waveforms; and complex-harmonic representation showing cardiac harmonics (example from [EyeFlow v2.9.10.1](#)).

Harmonic-domain descriptors are attractive Tier-1 candidates because they are compact (often dimensionless), naturally QC-gated (via harmonic SNR/coverage, coherence, and beat stability), and

map to distinct aspects of waveform morphology. In particular, complex-harmonic analysis separates complementary information channels: (i) **amplitude structure** (e.g., spectral roll-off / damping, relative high-frequency richness, and harmonic balance such as second-harmonic prominence), (ii) **phase organisation** through global-shift-invariant phase-coupling descriptors (“shape phase”) and robust phase-based delays, and (iii) **harmonic-derived time summaries** obtained by deterministic band-limited synthesis (e.g., centroid timing and VTI-style stroke-distance partitions) without fragile point picking. A practical advantage is that Doppler holography often provides several reliable cardiac harmonics (typically up to $n \approx 10$ in high-SNR segments) from a single short acquisition, enabling robust morphology summaries that are difficult to obtain with other ocular modalities.

2 Scientific objectives

The internship targets a compact, reproducible Tier-1 panel that can be frozen early and deployed across sites and indications.

1. **Specify a Tier-1 “shape panel”** from velocity harmonics up to $n \leq 10$, including normalisation and noise-floor correction.
2. **Design visit-level QC gates** so metrics are not driven by noise, motion, or failed beat-locking (explicit validity flags).
3. **Quantify uncertainty and repeatability** (per-visit confidence intervals; test–retest reliability on repeated acquisitions).
4. **Implement and integrate** the panel into the analysis pipeline and standard report (open-source PR, unit/regression tests, benchmark pack).
5. **Demonstrate utility** on existing datasets via pilot contrasts (healthy vs disease; optional provocation/flicker if available).

3 Tier-1 pulse waveform shape metrics

Tier-1 intent and metric contract. Tier-1 metrics provide *transportable, dimensionless or directly interpretable* descriptors of arterial pulse shape derived from the complex cardiac harmonics of a beat-locked velocity waveform. Metrics are computed per QC-valid vessel segment, then robustly aggregated at eye level (QC-filtered median), reported with (i) uncertainty (bootstrap over beats and segments) and (ii) coverage indicators (number of valid segments and valid harmonics). Each metric has explicit validity conditions; if conditions fail, the metric is *flagged missing* (never imputed).

Harmonic representation (shared definitions). Let $v_A(t)$ be the beat-locked arterial velocity waveform over one cardiac period T , and let V_n denote its complex harmonic coefficients at harmonic n of the cardiac frequency ($\omega_0 = 2\pi/T$, $\omega_n = n\omega_0$). We write $V_n = |V_n|e^{i\phi_n}$, with V_0 the DC component (mean level). Unless stated otherwise, Tier-1 harmonic metrics are expressed using V_1 -normalised quantities to reduce amplitude dependence:

$$X_n = \frac{V_n}{V_1}, \quad n = 1..N, \quad (1)$$

so that $X_1 = 1$. Harmonics are evaluated over $n = 1..N$ with $N = 10$ by default.

Harmonic reliability weights. Let $w_n \in [0, 1]$ denote a harmonic reliability weight derived from SNR/coherence and beat stability; $w_n = 0$ masks an invalid harmonic. When a binary mask is sufficient, we use $w_n = \mathbf{1}_{\text{QC}_n}$. Metric-specific weighting is avoided; a single w_n is preferred for interpretability and auditability.

Table 1: Tier-1 **core pulse-shape metrics from complex harmonics** (dimensionless unless stated). Metrics are computed per QC-valid vessel segment, then aggregated at eye level (QC-filtered median), with uncertainty and coverage indicators.

Metric	Symbol	Intent / interpretation
Second-harmonic prominence	H_2	Strength of the second harmonic relative to the fundamental (sharpness / reflection-compatible morphology): $H_2 = V_2 / V_1 = X_2 $.
Phase-coupling (2nd harmonic)	$\Delta\phi_2$	Global-shift-invariant “shape phase” at $n = 2$: $\Delta\phi_2 = \text{wrap}(\phi_2 - 2\phi_1)$; compact descriptor of asymmetry/sharpness (reported only if phase stable).
Phase-coupling (3rd harmonic)	$\Delta\phi_3$	Same as above for $n = 3$: $\Delta\phi_3 = \text{wrap}(\phi_3 - 3\phi_1)$ (optional; reported only if reliable coverage at $n = 3$).
Relative pulsatility (PI-like)	R_{10}	Pulsatility relative to mean level: $R_{10} = V_1 /V_0$ (requires $V_0 > 0$). Complements time-domain PI/RI; interpretation depends on compartment and indication.
Harmonic richness (2–10)	$\text{HRI}_{2:10}$	Relative high-frequency content beyond the fundamental: $\text{HRI}_{2:10} = \sum_{n=2}^{10} V_n / V_1 = \sum_{n=2}^{10} X_n $. Higher values indicate limited damping / more “sawtooth-like” shape.
Noise-corrected richness (2–10)	$\widetilde{\text{HRI}}_{2:10}$	Richness corrected for an estimated noise floor to reduce bias when high harmonics approach noise: $\widetilde{\text{HRI}}_{2:10} = \sum_{n=2}^{10} w_n V_n /(w_1 V_1)$, with $ \widetilde{V}_n = (V_n - \widehat{N}_n)_+$.
Harmonic decay slope (1–10)	$s_{1:10}$	Compact damping descriptor: slope of a linear fit of $\log V_n $ vs $\log n$ over $n = 1..10$ (reported only if sufficient valid harmonics). More negative slope indicates stronger damping/smoothier waveform.
Spectral centroid (1–10)	n_c	Energy location across harmonics using p_n (defined below). Higher n_c indicates energy shifted toward higher harmonics.
Spectral bandwidth (1–10)	σ_n	Spread of harmonic content around n_c : separates broad vs peaked spectra.
Spectral entropy (1–10)	H_{spec}	Complexity of harmonic distribution: higher values indicate more evenly distributed energy.
Spectral flatness (1–10)	F_{spec}	Peakedness vs flatness of the harmonic distribution; low values indicate dominance of few harmonics, high values indicate flatter spectra (noise-aware).

3.1 Core harmonic and spectral-shape descriptors

Spectral-distribution definitions. Define a weighted normalised distribution over $n = 1..10$:

$$p_n = \frac{w_n |V_n|}{\sum_{k=1}^{10} w_k |V_k|}, \quad (2)$$

and compute

$$n_c = \sum_{n=1}^{10} n p_n, \quad \sigma_n = \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^{10} (n - n_c)^2 p_n}, \quad H_{\text{spec}} = - \sum_{n=1}^{10} p_n \log(p_n + \varepsilon), \quad (3)$$

with $\varepsilon > 0$ a fixed numerical constant. Spectral flatness is

$$F_{\text{spec}} = \frac{\exp\left(\frac{1}{10} \sum_{n=1}^{10} \log(p_n + \varepsilon)\right)}{\frac{1}{10} \sum_{n=1}^{10} (p_n + \varepsilon)}. \quad (4)$$

3.2 Stability and band-limited morphology (supporting Tier-1 descriptors)

4 Time constants of a given waveform

Endpoint intent. We report complementary timing descriptors that summarise pulsatile dynamics from a beat-locked arterial waveform: (i) **phase-based delays** from harmonic phases, reported as

Table 2: Tier-1 **supporting pulse-shape descriptors** (primarily QC / interpretability support).

Metric	Symbol	Intent / interpretation
Beat-to-beat amplitude stability	$CV(V_n)$	Beat variability of harmonic magnitudes: $CV(V_n) = \text{std}_b(V_{n,b})/\text{mean}_b(V_{n,b})$ (reported typically for $n = 1, 2$).
Beat-to-beat phase-coupling stability	$\sigma_{\Delta\phi_n}$	Beat variability of phase-coupling (typically $n = 2$): $\sigma_{\Delta\phi_n} = \text{std}_b(\text{wrap}(\phi_{n,b} - n\phi_{1,b}))$; flags poor beat-locking or irregular rhythm.
Band-limited waveform (definition)	$\hat{v}(t)$	Deterministic band-limited inverse synthesis from accepted harmonics: $\hat{v}(t) = V_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{10} w_n (V_n e^{in\omega_0 t} + V_n^* e^{-in\omega_0 t})$.
Band-limited crest factor	CF	Time-domain sharpness on $\hat{v}(t)$: $CF = \max_t \hat{v}(t)/\text{rms}_t(\hat{v}(t))$.
Effective duty-cycle	D_α	Fraction of cycle above a fixed relative threshold: $D_\alpha = \text{frac}_t[\hat{v}(t) > V_0 + \alpha \text{std}_t(\hat{v}(t))]$ with pre-specified α .

Table 3: Tier-1 **pulse waveform time metrics** derived from complex harmonics and band-limited reconstructions.

Metric	Symbol	Intent / interpretation
Damping time constant (aggregate)	τ_P	Phase-aware scalar summary of vascular damping and phase lag, estimated from complex harmonics under explicit validity gates (first-order model fit).
Magnitude-derived damping time constant (aggregate)	τ_H	Scalar proxy of low-pass damping from harmonic magnitudes only. Larger τ_H indicates stronger attenuation of higher harmonics (smoother waveform).
Phase-derived equivalent delay (robust aggregate)	τ_ϕ	Amplitude-insensitive timing descriptor from harmonic phases: robust aggregate of per-harmonic delays $\tau_{\phi,n} = -\arg(X_n)/\omega_n$ over QC-accepted harmonics (median or weighted median).
Global phase-slope delay (group delay)	τ_G	Robust global delay estimated as the slope of (unwrapped) $\arg(X_n)$ vs ω_n (weighted least squares over QC-accepted harmonics).
Systolic-lobe centroid time (first moment)	$\tau_{M,1}$	Point-free timing: centroid (center-of-mass) of the systolic lobe from a band-limited waveform using a positive weight $w(t)$ within a fixed systolic window.
Systolic-lobe higher-order moments	$\tau_{M,n}$	Higher moments ($n \geq 2$) summarise lobe width and asymmetry (e.g., dispersion proxy $\sigma_M^2 = \tau_{M,2} - (\tau_{M,1})^2$).

a robust per-harmonic aggregate τ_ϕ and a global phase-slope (group-delay) estimate τ_G (Sec. 4.2); (ii) **moment-based timing** descriptors that avoid point picking, reported as systolic-lobe centroid time $\tau_{M,1}$ and higher moments $\tau_{M,n}$ (Sec. 4.3); and (iii) an **aggregated pulsatile time constant** τ_P that captures the combined effect of **vascular damping** (harmonic attenuation) and **phase lag** under a first-order damping model, accompanied by a magnitude-only diagnostic τ_H (Sec. 4.4). Time metrics are summarised in Table 3.

4.1 Beat locking and complex harmonics

Let $v_A(t)$ denote the arterial velocity waveform in a QC-valid vessel segment. Beat anchor times $\{t_k\}$ are obtained from a band-limited version of $v_A(t)$ using the maximum systolic upstroke per cycle, $t_k = \arg \max \dot{v}_A(t)$ within each beat. A robust beat-locked waveform is formed by a QC-filtered median across accepted beats after time-normalisation to a common cycle duration T . Complex harmonic coefficients V_n follow from the discrete Fourier series of the beat-locked pulse. We denote the cardiac fundamental by $\omega_0 = 2\pi/T$ and $\omega_n = n\omega_0$.

4.2 Phase-based time measures

We use the V_1 -normalised harmonics $X_n = V_n/V_1$ (Eq. 1) and write $\phi_n = \arg(X_n)$.

Per-harmonic equivalent delay $\tau_{\phi,n}$ and robust aggregate τ_ϕ .

$$\tau_{\phi,n} = -\frac{\phi_n}{\omega_n}, \quad n \in \mathcal{N}_{\text{QC}} \subset \{2, \dots, N\}. \quad (5)$$

We aggregate robustly across QC-accepted harmonics:

$$\tau_\phi = \text{median}_{n \in \mathcal{N}_{\text{QC}}} \tau_{\phi,n}, \quad (6)$$

optionally as a weighted median using weights w_n .

Global delay from phase slope (group delay) τ_G . After phase unwrapping across harmonic index n (when required), we fit

$$\phi_n \approx -\omega_n \tau_G + b \quad (7)$$

by weighted least squares:

$$(\hat{\tau}_G, \hat{b}) = \arg \min_{\tau_G, b} \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}_{\text{QC}}} w_n (\phi_n + \omega_n \tau_G - b)^2. \quad (8)$$

4.3 Centroid time and moment-based descriptors of the systolic lobe

We compute weighted moments of the main systolic lobe using a band-limited waveform $\hat{v}(t)$ derived from accepted harmonics (Table 2). Over a fixed systolic window \mathcal{T} , define a positive weight function (one robust choice):

$$w(t) = \max(\hat{v}(t) - v_{\text{base}}, 0) \mathbf{1}_{t \in \mathcal{T}}, \quad (9)$$

and moments

$$\tau_{\text{M},n} = \frac{\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} w(t) t^n}{\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} w(t)}, \quad n = 1, 2, \dots \quad (10)$$

(with sums over the sampled time grid). The centroid time is $\tau_{\text{M},1}$; a dispersion proxy is

$$\sigma_{\text{M}}^2 = \tau_{\text{M},2} - (\tau_{\text{M},1})^2. \quad (11)$$

4.4 First-order vascular damping model and estimation

We model the harmonic transfer with a first-order damping model

$$H(\omega; \tau) = \frac{1}{1 + i\omega\tau}. \quad (12)$$

Using $X_n = V_n/V_1$, a per-harmonic complex-fit estimate is

$$\tau_{\text{P},n} = \arg \min_{\tau > 0} |X_n - H(\omega_n; \tau)|^2, \quad n = 2..N, \quad (13)$$

and the aggregate is

$$\tau_{\text{P}} = \frac{\sum_{n=2}^N w_n \tau_{\text{P},n}}{\sum_{n=2}^N w_n}. \quad (14)$$

A magnitude-only diagnostic is

$$\tau_{\text{H},n} = \frac{1}{\omega_n} \sqrt{\frac{1}{|X_n|^2} - 1}, \quad (15)$$

valid only when $|X_n| \leq 1$, and aggregated as

$$\tau_{\text{H}} = \frac{\sum_{n=2}^N w_n \tau_{\text{H},n}}{\sum_{n=2}^N w_n}. \quad (16)$$

Table 4: Tier-1 **velocity–time integral (VTI) metrics** computed from the band-limited waveform $\hat{v}(t)$ (stroke-distance style).

Metric	Symbol	Intent / interpretation
Arterial VTI (stroke distance)	AVTI	Primary arterial stroke-distance proxy (non-negative): $AVTI = \int_0^T \max(\hat{v}(t) - v_{\text{base}}, 0) dt$. Provides a scale for normalisation and partition metrics.
First-half VTI	$VTI_{0 \rightarrow T/2}$	Early-cycle stroke distance: integral of the positive, baseline-referenced lobe over $[0, T/2]$ after upstroke alignment.
Second-half VTI	$VTI_{T/2 \rightarrow T}$	Late-cycle stroke distance: integral over $[T/2, T]$; sensitive to diastolic tail / runoff and reflected-wave contributions.
Normalised first-half fraction	F_{VTI}	Scale-free partition: $F_{VTI} = VTI_{0 \rightarrow T/2} / VTI_{0 \rightarrow T}$.
VTI asymmetry index (optional)	I_{VTI}	Signed asymmetry in $[-1, 1]$ (renamed to avoid symbol collision): $I_{VTI} = (VTI_{0 \rightarrow T/2} - VTI_{T/2 \rightarrow T}) / (VTI_{0 \rightarrow T/2} + VTI_{T/2 \rightarrow T})$.
Early/late VTI ratio (optional)	R_{VTI}	Partition imbalance: $R_{VTI} = VTI_{0 \rightarrow T/2} / (VTI_{T/2 \rightarrow T} + \varepsilon)$.
Signed VTI (optional diagnostic)	$VTI_{0 \rightarrow T}^{\pm}$	Signed integral $\int_0^T \hat{v}(t) dt$; captures net forward minus reverse contribution if sign inversions exist.
Absolute VTI (optional diagnostic)	$VTI_{0 \rightarrow T}^{\text{abs}}$	Absolute integral $\int_0^T \hat{v}(t) dt$; total excursion independent of sign.

5 Phase-partitioned stroke distance (VTI) metrics

Definition (velocity–time integral; “stroke distance”). From the beat-aligned, band-limited arterial velocity waveform $\hat{v}(t)$ over one cardiac period T , we define the per-beat arterial velocity–time integral (stroke distance) as

$$AVTI = \int_0^T \max(\hat{v}(t) - v_{\text{base}}, 0) dt, \quad (17)$$

so the primary stroke-distance metric is non-negative and robust to brief sign inversions. (A signed integral can be reported as an optional diagnostic.)

To capture within-cycle morphology asymmetry without requiring valve timing, we align the waveform at the maximum upstroke

$$t_0 = \arg \max_{t \in [0, T)} \frac{d\hat{v}}{dt}(t), \quad (18)$$

set $t = 0$ at t_0 (circular shift), and compute phase-partitioned VTIs:

$$VTI_{0 \rightarrow T/2} = \int_0^{T/2} \max(\hat{v}(t) - v_{\text{base}}, 0) dt, \quad VTI_{T/2 \rightarrow T} = \int_{T/2}^T \max(\hat{v}(t) - v_{\text{base}}, 0) dt. \quad (19)$$

Normalised partition fraction and optional descriptors. We report the dimensionless early-half fraction

$$F_{VTI} = \frac{VTI_{0 \rightarrow T/2}}{VTI_{0 \rightarrow T}}, \quad (20)$$

and optional descriptors: asymmetry index (renamed to avoid collision with AVTI)

$$I_{VTI} = \frac{VTI_{0 \rightarrow T/2} - VTI_{T/2 \rightarrow T}}{VTI_{0 \rightarrow T/2} + VTI_{T/2 \rightarrow T}} \in [-1, 1], \quad (21)$$

and early/late ratio

$$R_{VTI} = \frac{VTI_{0 \rightarrow T/2}}{VTI_{T/2 \rightarrow T} + \varepsilon}. \quad (22)$$

5.1 Quality gates, aggregation, and reporting (Tier-1)

Visit-level validity gates. Tier-1 metrics are reported only if the visit passes all required gates: (i) stable beat-locking / heart-rate (no gross cycle-to-cycle drift); (ii) acceptable motion/blur (acquisition QC); (iii) sufficient SNR at the fundamental ($n = 1$) in a minimum number of segments.

Harmonic-level validity gates. A harmonic n is considered valid only if: (i) $\text{SNR}_n \geq \text{SNR}_{\min}$ (and/or coherence above threshold), (ii) beat-to-beat phase dispersion is below threshold for phase-dependent metrics, and (iii) the harmonic is not dominated by estimated noise floor ($|V_n| > \hat{N}_n$ when required). Invalid harmonics are masked via $w_n = 0$.

Metric-specific validity. Phase metrics ($\Delta\phi_n, \tau_\phi, \tau_G$) additionally require phase stability (low $\sigma_{\Delta\phi_n}$ and/or low dispersion of ϕ_n across beats). R_{10} requires $V_0 > 0$. Slope-based metrics (e.g. $s_{1:10}, \tau_G$) require a minimum number of valid harmonics.

Aggregation and uncertainty. Per-segment values are aggregated to eye level using the QC-filtered median. Uncertainty is reported using bootstrap resampling over beats and segments. Coverage indicators include: number of valid segments, number of valid beats, and per-harmonic validity counts. If a gate fails, the corresponding metric is flagged missing (no imputation).

6 Open resources

1. Dataset: [10.5281/zenodo.16761111](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761111).
2. Hologram rendering: [HoloDoppler](#).
3. Quantitative analysis: [EyeFlow](#).

References

- [1] Yann Fischer, Zacharie Auray, Olivier Martinache, Marius Dubosc, Noé Topéza, Chloé Magnier, Maxime Boy-Arnould, and Michael Atlan. Retinal arterial blood flow measured by real-time doppler holography at 33,000 frames per second. In *2024 16th Biomed. Eng. International Conference (BMEiCON)*, pages 1–5. IEEE, 2024. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2409.17180>, doi:10.48550/arXiv.2409.17180.